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Agriculture of the future

According to the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO), we will have to increase the agricultural production for 70% by the year 2050, if we want to feed the world's growing population. Across the history, we have managed to increase the productivity with the aid of innovations in agricultural machinery, agrochemicals and novel practices of land cultivation, but today, our biggest ally are information technologies – artificial intelligence, robotics, Internet of Things, 3D printing, nanotechnologies and many more. We are witnesses of the 4th industrial revolution and a huge breakthrough of personal computers, internet, sensors and smart devices in our daily lives, but these technologies have an immense potential in agriculture as well. Electromagnetic probes are giving us in-depth information about soil, we are using sensors to monitor leaf wetness and the amount of minerals, while satellites and UAVs are giving us a comprehensive insight into the state of crops. Using advanced methods of machine learning and artificial intelligence, we are able to analyse massive datasets and extract new knowledge about the agricultural production and growth of crops. Furthermore, we use this knowledge to give an answer to practical questions concerning the agricultural production. Following the concept of precision agriculture, we are giving recommendations for fertilisation, irrigation and pesticide application on a metre resolution. In this way we are making sure that every plant receives a custom-tailored treatment, resources are used responsibly, risk is lowered and the yield is increased.

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ing organism interaction

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standing of processes describing biosphere-
Achievement of this goal is based on full
ady experimental base consists of atmospheric
re: a) ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis and weather
g Service of Serbia in plant protection (PIS)
d forest database (Harvard, MA, USA) and e)
). Biological observations and measurements
quito surveillance conducted by PFNS (Novi
ontenegro); b) plant and harmful organism
forest data base (Harvard, MA, USA), d)
§ (Novi Sad, Serbia) and e) COMBIRISK data
gy Fund).

energy, gas and momentum fluxes exchange,
f turbulent transfer between plant canopy and

g harmful organism appearance while monthly
nt forecasting;
ctors limiting the establishment of invasive
nd abundance.

data, modelling, harmful organism, plant